

A new PVC based membrane sensor of dibenzo-18-crown-6 for strontium

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Dibenzo-18-crown-6 crown ether is found to exhibit quite promising selectivity for Sr^{2+} ions. It can be used to estimate strontium in the range 5.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm^{-3} (0.28 to 8.76×10^{-3} mg dm^{-3}) with a near-Nernstian slope of 28 mV per decade of concentration. The working pH range of the proposed sensor is 2.0–6.0 with a response time of 25 s. The sensor can be used for more than three months in aqueous as well as in partially non-aqueous media. The practical utility of the membrane sensor has also been observed in solutions contaminated with detergent matter.

Relatively little work has been done on the development of ISEs for Sr^{2+} ion. The first useful Sr^{2+} selective electrode was developed by Baumann¹ using strontium complex of polyethylene glycol as electroactive material. The electrode was selective towards Sr^{2+} over Ca^{2+} and other bivalent cations with the exception of Ba^{2+} and Hg^{2+} . Srivastava and Jain² reported a heterogeneous membrane using hydrous thorium oxide embedded in polystyrene, while Jain *et al.*³ used strontium tungstoarsenate in araldite for Sr^{2+} selective electrodes and the same has been used as an end-point indicator in the potentiometric titration involving Sr^{2+} ions against ammonium dihydrogen phosphate. Attiyat *et al.*⁴ also reported benzo-18-crown-6 and its lariat ether based sensors for the estimation of K^+ , Sr^{2+} and Pb^{2+} . Here, we report the electroanalytical applications of poly(vinyl chloride) based membrane of dibenzo-18-crown-6 selective for Sr^{2+} ions. The proposed sensor is substantially free from the effect of normal interferents, e.g. Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Ba^{2+} .

Results and Discussion

The static response time of the membrane sensor observed is 25 s in the entire working concentration range. The membrane sensor exhibits a linear response in the concentration range of 5.0×10^{-6} to 1.0×10^{-1} mol dm^{-3} with a near-Nernstian slope of 28 mV per decade of concentration. The membrane electrodes were used over a period of 3 months without significant deviation in potentials. The membrane was repeatedly monitored at a fixed concentration of the test solution and the standard deviation of twenty identical measurements record is 0.5 mV.

The pH range, in which the proposed electrode assembly can be used, was determined by observing potentials at different levels of hydrogen ion concentration. Potentials do not change in the pH range 2.0–6.0. A sharp change in potentials beyond this range may be attributed to the protonation of crown ether.

The applicability of the proposed sensor in partially non-aqueous medium using methanol-water and ethanol-water has been observed. The electrode assembly can only be used in non-aqueous medium when its content is not more than 30%. Potentials vs $[\text{Sr}^{2+}]$ plots obtained in presence of various concentrations of cationic surfactant CTAB (cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide) shows a decrease in concentration range and slope with increase in the concentration of surfactant ions. Thus at higher concentrations of the surfactant the electrode assembly does not work satisfactorily.

Fig. 1. Plots showing selectivity coefficient values ($K_{A,B}^{Pot}$) at 1.00×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} concentration of interfering ions with respect of Sr^{2+} ions.

The practical utility of the sensor has also been observed by using it as an end-point indicator in the titration of Sr^{2+} ions with ammonium dihydrogen orthophosphate.

The potentiometric selectivity coefficients were determined by fixed interference method at 1.0×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} concentration of interfering ions. It is evident (Fig. 1) from the values of selectivity coefficients ($K_{\text{Sr}^{2+}, \text{B}}^{\text{Pot}}$) that the bivalent and trivalent cations does not interfere at any level

Table 1. Optimization of membrane ingredients

Membrane no.	Composition in ratio			Working concn. range $\times 10^{-3}$ (mg dm^{-3})	Slope (mV decade $^{-1}$ of concn.)
	Dibenzo-18-crown-6	PVC	Dibutyl phthalate		
1	1	8	1	1.89-8.76	22
2	1	10	1	0.88-8.76	24
3	1	12	1	0.28-8.76	28
4	1	15	1	3.49-8.76	21
5	1	18	1	4.93-8.76	21
6	1	12	1.5	0.55-8.76	24
7	1	12	2	8.76-8.76	20
8	2	12	1	15.58-8.76	19

of concentration. The selectivity coefficient values for monovalent ions are also lower in comparison to the limiting selectivity coefficient value at which an interfering ion exhibits the same response as the primary ion. Thus, the proposed sensor is substantially free from the effect of normal interferents like Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Ba^{2+} . The monovalent cations have a little higher value of selectivity coefficients but these also may not interfere with the working of the electrode assembly unless their concentration exceeds many fold with the concentration of the primary ion.

Experimental

Dibenzo-18-crown-6 (Fluka) was used as such. All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for the preparation of solutions.

Preparation of membrane and emf measurement : A large number of PVC-matrix membranes were prepared as reported earlier⁵ by dissolving crown ether (dibenzo-18-crown-6), PVC and plasticizer (dibutyl phthalate) in different proportions in THF (Table 1). After thoroughly stirring the mixture and allowing the bubbles to escape, it was poured carefully in the glass casting ring rested on a plate and left for a sufficient time to allow the solvent to evaporate. The glass ring with adhering membrane was carefully removed from the glass plate and stored for a day to allow complete evaporation. The membrane was cut away from the inner edge of the ring and glued to one end of a 'pyrex' glass tube with Araldite. The membrane was equilibrated with 1.0 mol dm^{-3} strontium nitrate solution for 72 h. The potential generated across the membrane was measured on a ECIL pH-potentiometer. The membrane having crown ether, PVC and plasticizer in the ratio 1 : 12 : 1 exhibited best working concentration range 0.28 to 8.76×10^{-3} mg dm^{-3} [Sr^{2+}] and a near-Nernstian slope of 28 mV per decade of [Sr^{2+}]. As such, all subsequent investigations were carried out with this particular membrane.

E.m.f. was measured by direct potentiometry at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ with the help of calomel electrode and KNO_3 salt-bridge. The performance of the electrode was investigated by measuring the potential of the solutions prepared in the concentration range 10^{-1} – 10^{-6} mol dm^{-3} by serial dilution.

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